

1 **Post-treatment of high-rate activated sludge effluent via zeolite adsorption and recovery of**
2 **ammonium-nitrogen as alternative fertilising products**

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12 **Highlights**

- 13 • A novel NH₄⁺ recovery system combining HRAS/CS and adsorption was tested.
14 • 70-80% of NH₄⁺ in HRAS/CS effluent was recovered in outputs after treating 140 BV.
15 • Zeolite and regeneration effluent also contained between 0.2-1.8 % K.
16 • Regeneration effluent from NH₄⁺ desorption could be applied in fertigation.
17 • N-saturated zeolite has potential as various fertilising products according to FPR.

18 **Abstract**

19 This study investigates the potential to connect nutrient flows between wastewater treatment and
20 agriculture through a two-stage nitrogen (N) recovery system composed of high-rate activated
21 sludge treatment in contact stabilisation mode (HRAS/CS) and column adsorption with zeolite.
22 The HRAS/CS process removes organic matter and suspended solids in wastewater, leaving N
23 behind in the effluent. The N was then successfully recovered with the zeolite column under
24 different scenarios, generating N and K-rich by-products. The regeneration effluent from the
25 zeolite column with KCl contained 60-845 mg NH₄⁺-N/L and 1.6-14.3 g K/L, having potential
26 for use as fertigation water. The N-saturated zeolite contained 1.5-8.4 mg N/g and 14.3-19.3 mg
27 K/g of the product fresh weight and low contaminant content, making them potentially eligible
28 as various fertilising products. Adsorption can thus concentrate N from HRAS/CS effluent and

29 produce by-products with potential agricultural value while meeting chemical oxygen demand
 30 and total nitrogen discharge standards.

31 **Keywords:** ammonium recovery, ion-exchange, high-rate contact-stabilization, municipal
 32 wastewater, circular economy

33 **Graphical Abstract**

34

35 **1. Introduction**

36 Conventional activated sludge (CAS) is the most common secondary treatment used to
 37 treat municipal wastewater (MWW) (Karna and Visvanathan, 2019), requiring a net energy input
 38 of 40 kWh per people equivalent (PE) per year (Zessner et al., 2010). This translates into an
 39 energy intensive MWW treatment sector in the European Union (EU), where 612 million PE of
 40 MWW were generated in 2016 (European Commission, 2020). This high energy demand is
 41 mainly linked to the oxidation of nitrogenous compounds into nitrogen gas (N_2) (Zessner et al.,
 42 2010). Moreover, this biological nutrient removal causes a fraction of nitrogen (N) to be emitted
 43 as nitrous oxide (N_2O) (Dockx et al., 2021), a 267-times more powerful greenhouse gas (GHG)
 44 than CO_2 (IPCC, 2013).

45 On the other hand, large amounts of energy are also being funnelled into the Haber-Bosch
 46 process to fix N_2 into ammonia (NH_3) to produce N fertilisers, accounting for 2% of total energy

47 use worldwide and 1.3% of global CO₂ emissions (IEA, 2021). Nutrient inputs from these
48 fertilisers cause an imbalance in the N cycle, contaminating water bodies and the atmosphere
49 (Battye et al., 2017). In order to mitigate the environmental issues caused by MWW treatment
50 and agricultural practices, EU legislation will introduce binding targets, including energy
51 neutrality for wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) by 2040 and reduction of GHG and nutrient
52 emissions from agriculture by 2030 (European Commission, 2019, 2022a; Grizzetti et al., 2023).

53 One of the ways current research tries to address the high cost and energy use in the
54 MWW treatment sector is by introducing adsorption into the wastewater treatment (WWT)
55 process, downstream of biological WWT, as a technique for N removal and, in some cases, N
56 recovery (Castro et al., 2021; Sheikh et al., 2023; Xiao et al., 2023). Adsorption has been tested
57 with various natural and synthetic adsorbents, such as biochar, zeolite, geopolymers and poly-
58 acrylic acid resins, which have proven to successfully remove N (up to a 95% removal efficiency
59 [RmE]) from various MWW streams (Huang et al., 2018). Many existing studies on the
60 adsorption of N from (pre-treated) MWW focus on optimising the process for N removal, with N
61 recovery techniques often being proposed, but seldom tested. In the few instances where the N
62 recovered in MWW-derived adsorption outputs is reported, there is only a limited
63 characterisation of the products and limited analyses of their marketability (He et al., 2022;
64 Maghfiroh et al., 2023; Sheikh et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2023). However, the mainstreaming of
65 N recovery and reuse is crucial to mitigate GHG and nutrient emissions from both the WWT and
66 agricultural sectors, as well as to successfully implement a circular economy that connects these
67 two sectors.

68 To fulfil the identified gaps in N recovery related to the current predominant emphasis on
69 N removal, a novel two-stage system was developed, combining high-rate activated sludge in

70 contact stabilisation mode (HRAS/CS) and adsorption (HRAS/CS+A) in order to treat MWW
71 and produce potential fertilising products. The HRAS process is less energy intensive than CAS
72 since it applies little to no aeration for the removal of organic matter and total suspended solids
73 (TSS) by favouring their redirection into sludge, rather than bio-oxidation. HRAS thus produces
74 more sludge that can be converted into energy. This is possible by applying high organic loading
75 rates (OLR) (>1 g biodegradable chemical oxygen demand [COD] per g volatile suspended
76 solids [VSS] per day) and a low solids retention time (SRT) (<5 d) (Meerburg et al., 2015).
77 Effluent from HRAS is thus ideal for N adsorption, since there is virtually no oxidation of N in
78 the process at such low SRTs (Rahman et al., 2020). Moreover, operation of HRAS in CS mode
79 induces feast-famine conditions that enhance the redirection of organic matter into sludge and its
80 biomethane production, compared to conventional HRAS and CAS systems (under continuous
81 feeding regimes) (Meerburg et al., 2015).

82 In the first stage of the proposed system, HRAS/CS was used to biologically oxidize
83 organic matter at a high rate with low total nitrogen (TN) removal, to reduce the energy input
84 and N₂O emissions related to aeration. In the second stage, N was recovered by an adsorption
85 column packed with zeolite, since the N-saturated zeolite can be applied directly to soil (Torma
86 et al., 2014), unlike synthetic materials. The production and marketability of two direct outputs
87 from N adsorption was then evaluated (for reduced reagent and energy use): N-saturated zeolite
88 and regeneration effluent. To the author's best knowledge, the integration of HRAS with
89 adsorption has only been previously tested once by applying a conventional HRAS system up-
90 stream of N adsorption and using more energy and reagent-intensive techniques to produce the N
91 recovery products (Sheikh et al., 2023).

92 To test the technical feasibility of developing such a system, this study focused on (i)
93 evaluating and optimizing the adsorption performance of a zeolite column in terms of N recovery
94 and concomitant treatment of HRAS/CS effluent, (ii) up-concentrating the N in the zeolite by
95 using one column to treat both HRAS/CS effluent and the liquid fraction of sewage sludge
96 digestate (LFD) (a stream with higher N concentration that could be generated from the
97 described system) in series, and (iii) characterising the potential function of the adsorption
98 outputs (N-saturated zeolite and regeneration effluent), according to the ‘Fertilising Product
99 Council regulation (EU) 2019/1009’ (2019) (FPR). Results from this research will provide
100 important data for upscaling the adsorption stage for N recovery, as well as insights into the
101 applicability of the generated outputs as fertilising products.

102 **2. Materials and Methods**

103 **2.1 Description of adsorption influents**

104 HRAS/CS effluent was used as influent for the adsorption process in order to produce
105 alternative fertilising products (see Section 2.2.3). This stream was produced in a sequencing
106 batch reactor (SBR) (Height/Diameter = 2.33) with a working volume of 378 L, treating 0.72-
107 1.08 m³ of MWW daily. The SBR was fed with MWW (treated by a 7 mm coarse grid) collected
108 in the full-scale municipal WWTP of Aartselaar (Belgium) which has a capacity of 54,000 PE
109 (60 g biochemical oxygen demand [BOD]/PE.d). The MWW is collected from urban sources in
110 Flanders and contains NH₄⁺-N in the range of 6.2-59 mg/L (25 mg N/L as average in 2021). The
111 SBR was operated in CS mode by including five phases of operation: stabilisation (max. 60 min,
112 with aeration), contact (i.e., feeding, without aeration) (15 min), mixing (15 min), settling (25
113 min) and discharge (5 min, sludge and treated effluent). In order to operate under high-rate
114 conditions, the SRT of the system was kept between 2-5 d and the OLR between 1-2 g bCOD/g
115 VSS.day.

116 Synthetic wastewaters (SWWs) simulating HRAS/CS effluent and LFD were also used as
117 influent for N recovery optimisation experiments. SWW was used to ensure a constant influent
118 composition to obtain comparable results. The SWW simulating HRAS/CS effluent (Sections
119 2.2.1-2.2.2 and 2.3) was made to contain 25 mg $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N/L}$, 25 mg $\text{K}^+\text{/L}$, 104 mg $\text{Na}^+\text{/L}$, 79 mg
120 $\text{Ca}^{2+}\text{/L}$ and 8 mg $\text{Mg}^{2+}\text{/L}$ ($\text{pH} = 5.8 \pm 0.1$). These concentrations were based on the estimated
121 average N content in HRAS/CS effluent (i.e., equal to the average N content in MWW, assuming
122 negligible removal) and measured cationic content. SWW simulating LFD (Section 2.3) was
123 prepared based on the characteristics of LFD generated in the Antwerpen South WWTP in
124 Belgium. The LFD-based SWW contained 1300 mg $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N/L}$, 25 mg $\text{K}^+\text{/L}$, 104 mg $\text{Na}^+\text{/L}$, 39
125 mg $\text{Ca}^{2+}\text{/L}$ and 1 mg $\text{Mg}^{2+}\text{/L}$ (at $\text{pH} 7.9$). All SWWs were prepared by using NH_4Cl , NaCl ,
126 $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and KH_2PO_4 .

127 **2.2 Nitrogen recovery from high-rate activated sludge effluent**

128 The adsorption experiments in this section were set up to evaluate the N recovery
129 efficiency of a zeolite column when treating HRAS/CS effluent, with views on testing the
130 feasibility of developing a novel two-stage WWT and N recovery system (Figure 1). All
131 adsorption columns used for the following experiments had dimensions of 20 x 1 cm, and were
132 packed with 10.2 g of washed zeolite (sieved at 0.05-1 mm) in its original ionic state (Z-O) (for a
133 10 mL packing volume). The zeolite was ordered from Zeocem® (fraction 0-1 mm), a company
134 that mines zeolite deposits in Slovakia.

135

136 **Figure 1.** Process flow and outputs of the proposed novel two-stage N recovery and wastewater
 137 treatment system (HRAS/CS and adsorption). Stage 1 shows certain parameters applied during
 138 pilot operation. Dashed lines show the additional treatment steps that could generate a liquid
 139 fraction of sludge digestate (LFD) from HRAS/CS for adsorption.

140 2.2.1 Effect of adsorption flow rate

141 Flow optimisation experiments were carried out to assess the effect of flow rate on N
 142 recovery by plotting and modelling their $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ breakthrough curves, which provided data
 143 regarding (i) the amount of volume of SWW that can be treated before the breakthrough volume
 144 is reached, (ii) the maximum N adsorption capacity (q_{max}) of the zeolite for the given conditions
 145 and (iii) the N adsorbed as a function of the volume treated until breakthrough (q_b). These
 146 variables are influenced by the initial concentration (C_0) of $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and the concentration of
 147 competing cations, therefore SWW mimicking HRAS/CS effluent (Section 2.1) was used for
 148 these experiments in order to maintain constant NH_4^+ and cation compositions. Four different

149 flow rates were tested in triplicate: 0.05 L/h, 0.1 L/h, 0.25 L/h and 0.4 L/h, equivalent to 5, 10,
 150 25 and 40 empty bed volumes (BV) per hour and an empty bed contact time (EBCT) of 12, 6, 2.4
 151 and 1.5 min, respectively. The empty bed volume of the zeolite bed was taken as reference for
 152 the BV unit (1 BV = 10 mL).

153 NH_4^+ -N concentrations were measured in discrete effluent samples (C_e) (Figure 1) of 11
 154 mL. From 0-80 BVs of SWW treated, discrete samples were taken at intervals of 40 BV; from
 155 80-120 BVs, at 20 BV intervals; and from 120-260 BV, at 10 BV intervals. The NH_4^+ -N
 156 breakthrough curves were modelled using the Thomas (Thomas, 1948), Bohart-Adams (BA)
 157 (Bohart and Adams, 1920) and Yoon-Nelson (YN) models (Yoon and Nelson, 1984). The
 158 linearised Thomas model (Eq.1), was used to calculate the constants q_0 and K_{Th} in order to model
 159 the breakthrough curve of the tested flow rates; the linearised BA model (Eq.2), to calculate the
 160 constants N_0 and K_{AB} ; and the linearised YN model (Eq. 3) was used to calculate the constants ,
 161 q_{YN} (Eq. 4) and K_{YN} .

$$C_e = \frac{C_o}{1 + e^{\frac{K_{Th}}{Q}(q_0 X - C_o V_{eff})}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$C_e = C_o * e^{(K_{BA} C_o t - k_b N_0 \frac{H}{u})} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$C_e = \frac{C_o e^{K_{YN} t - \tau K_{YN}}}{1 + e^{K_{YN} t - \tau K_{YN}}} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$q_{YN} = \frac{C_o Q \tau}{1000 X} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

162
 163 Where C_e is the NH_4^+ -N concentration (mg/L) in the discrete effluent samples; C_o is the
 164 initial NH_4^+ -N concentration; q_0 is q_{max} (mg N/g zeolite); K_{Th} is the Thomas kinetic constant

165 (L/(mg·min); X is the amount of material in the column (g zeolite); Q is the volumetric flow rate
166 (mL/min); V_{eff} is the effluent volume (L); K_{BA} is the BA kinetic constant (L/mg.min); N_0 is the
167 adsorption capacity of the solid phase (mg/L zeolite); u is the hydraulic loading rate (cm/min); H
168 is the adsorbent height in the column (cm); K_{YN} is the YN kinetic constant (1/min); τ is the time
169 point at which 50% of $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N } C_0$ is detected in the column effluent; q_{YN} is q_{max} (mg N/g zeolite)
170 and t is the sampling time.

171 Modelling results for Z-O were validated by (i) comparing the breakthrough curves and
172 calculated breakthrough points with the experimental data, (ii) using the models to predict the
173 breakthrough point for experiments in Section 2.2.2 and (iii) treating 390 BV of SWW (175 BV
174 after C_c levels off at 0.7-0.8 C_0) in order to measure q_{max} experimentally (at a flow rate of 40
175 BV/h). The breakthrough point (or volume) was defined as the volume of column influent that
176 could be treated before the cumulative $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentration (C_c) in the effluent reached 20% of
177 the $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N } C_0$ (equivalent to an RmE of 80%). This set-point was chosen according to the
178 ‘Urban Waste Water Treatment Council Directive 91/271/EEC’ (1991) (UWWTD) and Flemish
179 (VLAREM II – Appendix 5.3.1) discharge limits stating that minimum 70% and 80%
180 (respectively) of the TN from MWW must be removed (with a maximum discharge
181 concentration of 15 mg N/L for urban WWTP with a capacity ranging from 10,000 – 100,000
182 PE).

183 2.2.2 Comparison of nitrogen recovery methods

184 Two N recovery strategies were assessed (in triplicate) for their effect on WWT and on
185 final N content in the adsorption outputs (N-saturated zeolite and regeneration effluent) when
186 treating synthetic HRAS/CS effluent. SWW was used once again to maintain a constant $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$
187 cationic composition to generate comparable results. Based on the results from $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$
188 breakthrough curve modelling (Section 2.2.1), the adsorption process (saturation and

189 regeneration cycles) was carried out at a flow rate of 40 BV/h and cumulative effluent samples
190 (during the saturation cycle) were taken after 100 and 140 BV, since the breakthrough volume
191 calculated with modelling results (using Eq. 5) was 152 BV. It was confirmed that the
192 breakthrough point was reached after treating 140 BV of SWW.

193 The first N recovery method (Method 1) consisted in one N adsorption cycle up to the
194 defined breakthrough point (140 BV) and the subsequent harvesting of the N-saturated zeolite
195 (without column regeneration). In Method 2, the N adsorption cycle (140 BV), was followed by
196 a column regeneration cycle and a final adsorption cycle of 140 BV. The regeneration cycle was
197 carried out (concurrently) with 3% (mass/volume) KCl until the decrease in discrete $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$
198 content in the regeneration effluent stabilised (between 2.5-0.8 mg/L), indicating full
199 regeneration of the zeolite was achieved. Before and after regeneration with KCl, the zeolite
200 column was rinsed with 10 mL of tap water to remove excess SWW and KCl solution,
201 respectively. With Method 2, the N-saturated zeolite was harvested after the last adsorption step
202 and two distinct fractions of regeneration effluent were collected. The 1st fraction consisted of
203 the 1st BV of regeneration solution (10 mL) and the 2nd fraction consisted of BVs between 1.1-
204 39.0 (380 mL).

205 In order to compare the two methods, the N content in the harvested N-saturated zeolite
206 and the regeneration effluent was measured and N mass balances, recovery efficiency (RcE) (Eq.
207 6) and RmE (Eq. 7) were also calculated. The different methods were also compared in terms of
208 cation content in effluent SWW, the quantity of adsorbent and chemical inputs required for
209 operation and quantity of outputs generated.

$$C_{c(i)} = \frac{\sum_{i=2} \bar{C}_{m(i,i-1)} \times (V_i - V_{i-1}) + \bar{C}_{m(i-1)} \times V_{(i-1)}}{(V_i)} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

$$RcE = \frac{Mass\ N_{influent}(g) - Mass\ N_{zeolites}(g)}{Mass\ N_{influent}(g)} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$RmE = \frac{C_o - C_c}{C_o} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

210 Where C_m is the modelled NH_4^+ -N concentration in the discrete effluent, \bar{C}_m is the average
 211 modelled NH_4^+ -N concentration, V is the volume of SWW treated, i designates volume intervals,
 212 RcE is the NH_4^+ -N recovery efficiency (%); RmE is the NH_4^+ -N removal efficiency (%); C_c is
 213 the NH_4^+ -N concentration in the cumulative effluent (mg/L) and C_o is the initial NH_4^+ -N
 214 concentration in the column influent.

215 2.2.3 Municipal wastewater treatment and production of alternative fertilising products

216 HRAS/CS effluent from the SBR pilot treating MWW (Section 2.1) was treated with
 217 adsorption using the N recovery methods described in Section 2.2.2 (in triplicate) to produce N-
 218 saturated zeolite and 40 BV of regeneration effluent, in order to take into account the effect of all
 219 the components present in this stream on fertilising product quality and WWT. The N mass
 220 balances, RcE (Eq. 6) and RmE (Eq. 7) were also calculated.

221 The influent used and the N-saturated zeolite, regeneration effluent and treated HRAS/CS
 222 effluent generated in these experiments were analysed for pH, electrical conductivity, humidity,
 223 NH_4^+ -N, NO_3^- -N, total organic carbon (TOC), total phosphorous (TP), TN, total sulphur (TS), Ca,
 224 Mg, Na, K, micronutrients (B, Co, Cu, Fe, Mn and Zn) and contaminants (As, Cd, Cr, Ni, Pb).
 225 The adsorption inputs and outputs were frozen in -20°C until analysed for the aforementioned
 226 parameters. The analysed physicochemical characteristics of the adsorption outputs were then
 227 evaluated against the FPR and the Regulation (EU) 2020/741' (2020) 'Minimum requirements
 228 for water reuse' (WRR) to determine their potential as alternative fertilising products (discussed
 229 in Section 3.3).

230 **2.3 Enhancing nitrogen recovery with the liquid fraction of sewage sludge digestate**

231 An additional N recovery method (Method 1b) was used to increase the N content in the
232 N-saturated zeolite obtained when treating synthetic HRAS/CS effluent by using synthetic LFD.
233 LFD is a higher-strength wastewater (i.e., wastewater with a significantly higher N
234 concentration) than HRAS/CS effluent that could be generated from the novel two-stage system
235 integrating HRAS/CS and adsorption (Figure 1). Method 1b consisted in two consecutive
236 adsorption cycles, with the first cycle being the same as Method 1 (Section 2.2.2) and the second
237 cycle using LFD-based SWW (Section 2.1) as influent to saturate the zeolite column up to 0.82
238 C_0 , after which the N-saturated zeolite was harvested and analysed. The same flow rate used for
239 the N recovery methods in Section 2.2.2 (40 BV/h) was applied. The N-saturated zeolite
240 obtained with this method was analysed for NH_4^+ -N content and N mass balances, R_{cE} (Eq. 6)
241 and R_{mE} (Eq. 7) were calculated. Additionally, the N content achieved on the N-saturated
242 zeolite with Method 1b was compared to the q_{max} of zeolite saturated with synthetic LFD. The
243 latter was measured experimentally by pumping 80 BV of the LFD through the zeolite and
244 measuring its final NH_4^+ -N content.

245 **2.4 Analytical Methods**

246 NH_4^+ -N, NO_3^- , TN, PO_4^{3-} and COD in liquid samples were analysed with
247 Spectrophotometry (Macherey-Nagel, Nanocolor test kits). In solid samples, NH_4^+ -N and NO_3^-
248 were extracted with 1M KCl and then measured with the cited test kits. TN and TOC in solid
249 samples was measured using Dumas Combustion (Skalar, PrismaCS100). Ca, Mg, Na and K in
250 liquid samples from SWW were analysed directly with Inductively Coupled Plasma – Optical
251 Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES), while nutrients (except TN, NH_4^+ -N, NO_3^- and PO_4^{3-}) and
252 contaminants in liquid samples from HRAS/CS effluent were analysed after digestion by
253 incubating 25 mL at room temperature overnight in 10 mL of concentrated aqua regia (1:3 ratio

254 of HNO₃ to HCl) and then for 2 h on a hot plate (103-133°C). For the same analyses, N-saturated
255 zeolite samples were digested with Ultrawave digestion (Milestone, Ultrawave ECR) in 5 mL of
256 reverse aqua regia (1:3 ratio of HCl to HNO₃) at 220°C for 30 min and then analysed with the
257 ICP-OES.

258 **3. Results and Discussion**

259 **3.1 Nitrogen recovery from high-rate activated sludge effluent**

260 3.1.1 Effect of adsorption flow rate

261 The experiments described in Section 2.2.1, were carried out to compare the influence of
262 different flow rates (5 BV/h, 10 BV/h, 25 BV/h and 40 BV/h) on the adsorption of NH₄⁺-N with
263 a Z-O column. The calculated parameters for the tested breakthrough curve models (Thomas,
264 Bohart-Adams and Yoon-Nelson) are shown in Table 1. From the R² values of the linear
265 regressions made with the linearized models, the Thomas and YN models best fit the
266 experimental data for all tested flows. These were further validated by (i) their alignment with
267 the experimental measurements used to feed the models (Figure 2), (ii) the experimental
268 measurement of q_{max} and (iii) the breakthrough volume results during the experiments for
269 nitrogen recovery comparison (Section 3.1.2). The validation experiment showed that the
270 measured q_{max} (after 392 BV of SWW treated) was similar to the modelled q_{max}, with the zeolite
271 adsorbing 3.8 mg NH₄⁺-N /g, or 105% of the modelled q_{max}. On the other hand, the results from
272 the BA model had very high deviation from the experimental measurements and will not be
273 further discussed.

274

275 **Table 1.** Calculated constants, R^2 values and adsorption capacity at the breakthrough point (q_b) for the
 276 Thomas, Yoon-Nelson and Bohart-Adams models, used to model the $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ breakthrough curve on
 277 zeolites at different flow rates (in bed volumes [BV]/h).

Parameters	Flow Rates (BV/h)			
	5	10	25	40
Thomas Model				
K_{Th} ($\text{L}^2/\text{mg}\cdot\text{min}$)	1.1E-04	2.2E-04	4.2E-04	6.1E-04
q_0 (mg/g)	3.9	4.0	3.8	3.6
R^2	0.89	0.80	0.75	0.85
q_b^a (mg/g)	3.7	3.7	3.3	2.9
Yoon-Nelson Model				
K_{YN} (L/min)	2.4E-03	5.0E-03	1.0E-02	1.1E-02
q_{YN} (mg/g)	3.9	4.1	3.8	3.6
τ (BV)	167	166	159	150
R^2	0.90	0.80	0.75	0.85
q_b^a (mg/g)	3.7	3.7	3.3	2.9
Bohart-Adams				
K_{BA} (L/mg.min)	6.5E-05	1.3E-04	1.2E-04	3.8E-04
N_0 (mg/L)	90.2	97.7	122	98.5
R^2	0.75	0.62	0.57	0.70
q_b^a (mg/g)	3.7	3.8	3.6	3.2

278 ^a $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ content on the zeolite at the breakthrough point calculated using the breakthrough curve models

279 The values predicted by the Thomas and YN models in this study for q_{max} (Table 1) and
 280 breakthrough volumes (Figure 2) show a decreasing trend as flow rate increases. Both models
 281 predict that the 10 BV/h flow rate leads to the highest q_{max} . However, the difference in q_{max}
 282 between all flow rates was low in general, ranging between 0.1-0.5 mg N/g. On the other hand,
 283 the breakthrough volumes show a higher variation, with both the 5 and 10 BV flow rates
 284 showing the highest treatment capacity. The capacity at 25 BV/h and 40 BV/h ranged between
 285 18.0-19.4 and 30.9-39.7 BVs less than the highest treatment capacity, respectively. The observed
 286 decrease in q_{max} and breakthrough volume can be attributed to the decrease in EBCT with
 287 increasing flow rates, allowing less time for the $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ to adsorb to the zeolites. This is

288 compatible with results from Gagliano et al. (2022), where they observed a slight decrease in
289 q_{\max} (3.24 to 3.04 mg/g) when lowering the EBCT from 8 to 4 min. Malovanyy et al. (2013)
290 determined a larger increase in q_{\max} (from 6.8 to 11.3 mg/g) and breakthrough volume, when
291 decreasing the flow rate from 31 BV/h to 17 BV/h, which might be attributable to a lower
292 competing cation content in their SWW and the ionic modification of their zeolite to Na^+ form
293 (Z-Na). Still, at the higher flow rates it is possible to treat MWW at a much faster rate (2.5 to 4
294 times faster, for a given volume), while the estimated loss of treatment capacity is small in
295 comparison (1.1 to 1.4 times less capacity). These results demonstrate that the adsorption system
296 can operate well within the range of 5-40 BV/h, which can thus be applied for the design of a
297 HRAS/CS+A system (Figure 1).

298 The modelled q_{\max} determined in this study for 10 BV/h (EBCT = 6 min) (Table 1)
299 corresponds with the q_{\max} estimated by Zhou et al. (2021), of 4.05 mg/g, during column
300 operation at an EBCT of 5 min, using a similar NH_4^+ -N C_0 to this study. However, higher q_{\max} ,
301 have also been determined for modified and non-modified natural zeolite breakthrough curves,
302 using SWW and MWW: 11.3 mg/g (Malovanyy et al., 2013), 4.0-6.6mg/g (Zhou et al. 2021),
303 and 5.4-8.1 mg/g (Pinelli et al., 2022). The higher q_{\max} achieved in some of these studies could
304 be due to (i) the higher initial NH_4^+ -N concentration used (40 mg/L) in SWW by Malovanyy et
305 al. (2013) and in spiked MWW by Pinelli et al. (2022). The breakthrough curve models applied
306 in this and other studies are dependent on the initial NH_4^+ -N C_0 used, as shown in Eq. 1 and Eq.
307 3, therefore the modelled q_{\max} on the zeolite will vary accordingly (increasing with an increase
308 in C_0). A lower competing cation concentration in the SWWs applied by Malovanyy et al.
309 (2013) (4 times lower Ca^{2+} and K^+) and Zhou et al. (2021) (1.3 times less Ca^{2+} , without K^+ or
310 Na^+ addition), compared to this study, could also contribute to an increase in NH_4^+ -N removal,

311 and thus q_{\max} , given K^+ , Na^+ and Ca^{2+} have previously shown an inhibitory effect on
312 ammonium removal (in decreasing order) (Fu et al., 2022). Variations related to the regional
313 source of the zeolite between this and the mentioned studies can also have a large effect on
314 q_{\max} , due to differences in their mineralogical characteristics (Jmayai et al. 2018). However,
315 regarding WWT capacity, this study achieved the treatment of more than 100 BVs (after 12-24 h
316 of operation) before the breakthrough point (according to C_e) was reached, while in other studies
317 breakthrough was achieved before 100 BV (Pinelli et al., 2022) or after a shorter treatment time
318 (Zhou et al. 2021) for similar EBCTs (5-15 min). The breakthrough plot from Pinelli et al., 2022
319 maintained a lower NH_4^+-N C_e until 75 BVs, while in this study, C_e began increasing around 75
320 BV. This could explain why less SWW could be treated before breakthrough by Pinelli et al.,
321 2022 and Zhou et al. 2021, while a higher q_{\max} could be estimated. If a larger fraction of NH_4^+-N
322 from each volume interval can adsorb to the zeolite in the beginning, this can result in a higher
323 q_{\max} , but also a faster occupation of the free surface area on the zeolite for adsorption.

324 It was also observed that τ (Table 1) is reached before the breakthrough volume when
325 taking NH_4^+-N C_c as reference (Figure 2) (i.e., cumulative concentration), according to the YN
326 model. This means that when the breakthrough point is set according to C_c , rather than C_e
327 (discrete concentration), more than 50% of the NH_4^+-N in the influent can be allowed to break
328 through in a given effluent volume interval while still meeting discharge limits. On the other
329 hand, when the breakthrough point is set according to C_e , a maximum of 20% of the influent
330 NH_4^+-N content can exit the column in any given effluent volume interval (Figure 2). Thus, more
331 MWW can be treated by the column and more NH_4^+ can become adsorbed to it when the C_c is
332 taken as reference for the breakthrough point. In practice, when upscaling this type of system, a
333 buffer tank could then be placed between the N adsorption column and the final discharge of

334 MWW to extend the lifetime of the zeolite packing for WWT and achieve a higher q_b . Finally, as
 335 the difference between the estimated breakthrough volume (according to C_c) and τ grows, the q_b
 336 of a column should also increase. According to the q_b (YN model), it can be expected that the
 337 zeolite would be the most saturated with N at breakthrough when applying a flow rate of 5 to 10
 338 BV/h (Table 1).

339
 340 **Figure 2.** Experimental and modelled (Thomas and Yoon-Nelson [YN] models) $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$
 341 breakthrough curves at four different flow rates (5, 10, 25 and 40 BV/h). Black lines indicate the
 342 breakthrough point calculated with the models (in BV and discrete $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentration),
 343 according to the cumulative $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentration; black dotted lines, the breakthrough point
 344 according to the discrete $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentration. Flows are expressed in empty bed volumes
 345 (BV)/h and volume in BV (where 1 empty BV= 10 mL).

346

347 3.1.2 Comparison of nitrogen recovery methods

348 The effect of two N recovery methods (described in Section 2.2.2) on WWT and N
349 content in adsorption outputs was investigated using SWW to eliminate effects related to
350 HRAS/CS effluent composition and NH_4^+ -N and cation concentrations. With Method 1
351 (adsorption without zeolite regeneration), a higher NH_4^+ -N RcE was achieved, compared to
352 Method 2 (adsorption with zeolite regeneration) (Table 2). Method 1 showed an N mass loss
353 from the system of 5%, while Method 2 a loss of 13%. This large difference might be due to the
354 fact that with Method 2, the column was cleaned between the adsorption and regeneration steps
355 and some mass of N might have been lost during these cleaning steps. The loss from Method 1 is
356 attributable to (i) the fraction of SWW that remains in the column when the run is ended and (ii)
357 NH_4^+ -N from the column that might become de-sorbed when the zeolites are washed previous to
358 filtration. Potential losses from NH_3 stripping were negligible, since the process pH and
359 temperature were 5.8 ± 0.06 and 19.6 ± 1.3 °C . Taking these effects into account, the measured
360 N content in the N-saturated zeolite and regeneration effluent is consistent with mass balance
361 results. Overall, the NH_4^+ -N RcE by the N-saturated zeolite was very close to the NH_4^+ -N RmE
362 from SWW (Table 2). The RmE for the 2 methods met current UWWTD discharge standards
363 (Section 2.2.1).

364 The N-saturated zeolite obtained from Methods 1 and 2 concentrated N from HRAS/CS
365 effluent by 106 and 93 times, respectively after treating a volume of 140 ± 5 BV. It was also
366 observed that some K^+ from SWW was also adsorbed (before zeolite regeneration) at a rate of
367 0.61 ± 0.03 mg/g, which adds to the nutrient RcE of the process. In Method 2, after the KCl
368 regeneration step, the NH_4^+ -N RmE and RcE from SWW dropped by 11 and 12%, respectively,
369 compared to what was achieved without regeneration, thus reducing the zeolite's adsorption and
370 WWT capacity.

371 **Table 2.** Efficiency of N recovery methods when using synthetic wastewater (SWW) and
 372 effluent from the HRAS/CS pilot system, in terms of (i) output quality (i.e., N content in N-
 373 saturated zeolite and regeneration effluent), (ii) N recovery and removal from SWW and
 374 HRAS/Cs effluent and (iii) operation (inputs/treated volume).

<i>Outputs produced with Synthetic Wastewater</i>					
Method and products	NH ₄ ⁺ -N concentration in influent(mg/L)	NH ₄ ⁺ -N concentration in adsorption outputs	NH ₄ ⁺ -N recovery ^a (%) and [g/kg.100 BV SWW treated]	NH ₄ ⁺ -N removal efficiency (%)	Inputs/Outputs ^b (BV/10 ³ BV SWW treated)
Method 1, N-saturated zeolite	23.7 ± 0.5	1.9 ± 0.1 g/kg FW	75 ± 2 [1.4 ± 0.1]	79 ± 1	7.1 ± 0.0
Method 2, regeneration effluent and N-saturated zeolite	23.3 ± 1.4 ^c	0.85 ± 0.09 g/L (Regeneration effluent, Fraction 1)	66 ± 2 [1.0 ± 0.1] ^c	80 ± 4 (AR cycle)	156.8 ± 1.3 ^c
		0.02 ± 0.00 g/L (Regeneration effluent, Fraction 2)		72 ± 3 (Final A cycle)	
		1.6 ± 0.1 g/kg FW (N-saturated zeolite)			
Method 1b, N-saturated zeolite	1321 ± 1 ^d	8.4 ± 0.1 g/kg FW	25 ± 1 [4.9 ± 0.1] ^d	25 ± 1 ^d	5.9 ± 0.0
<i>Alternative fertilising products produced with HRAS/CS effluent</i>					
Method and products	NH ₄ ⁺ -N [TN] ^e concentration in influent (mg/L)	NH ₄ ⁺ -N concentration in adsorption outputs	NH ₄ ⁺ -N recovery ^a (%) and [g/kg.100 BV wastewater treated]	NH ₄ ⁺ -N [TN] removal efficiency (%)	Treated Volume (BV)
Method 1, N-saturated zeolite	12.0 ± 1.4	1.4 ± 0.1 g/kg FW	84 ± 2 [0.7 ± 0.1]	79 ± 0	196.7 ± 5.8
Method 1, N-saturated zeolite	36.1 ± 4.0 [50 ± 1]	2.4 ± 0.0 g/kg FW	82 ± 1 [2.2 ± 0.0]	84 ± 1 [77 ± 1]	104.7 ± 1.0
Method 2 – regeneration effluent	27.9 ± 0.1 [34 ± 1]	0.78 ± 0.02 g/L (Fraction 1) 0.06 ± 0.00 g/L (Fraction 2)	88 ± 1 [0.4 ± 0.0] (AR cycle)	82 ± 1 (AR cycle) [76 ± 2]	132.2 ± 1.8 (AR cycle)
Method 2 – N-saturated zeolite	24.95 ± 1.8 [35 ± 1]	1.6 ± 0.1 g/kg FW (N-saturated zeolite)	97 ± 1 [0.7 ± 0.0] (Final A cycle)	82 ± 1 (Final A cycle) [74 ± 4]	90.3 ± 2.1 (Final A cycle)

375 A = adsorption; AR = adsorption-regeneration; BV = bed volumes

376 ^a Nitrogen recovery is expressed in terms of recovery efficiency and (in brackets) of the mass of N that can be recovered
 377 per mass of zeolite in a column after 100 BV of wastewater treated

378 ^b The inputs considered for a full N recovery cycle are the zeolite packing material and KCl solution for regeneration. The
 379 input quantity is the same as the output (product) quantity: N-saturated zeolite and regeneration effluent.

380 ^c Data for a full cycle (AR and final A cycle) producing N-saturated zeolite and regeneration effluent

381 ^d Data from only the final saturation cycle (with the liquid fraction of sewage sludge digestate)

382 ^e TN concentration in HRAS/CS effluent is shown in brackets

383

384 The difference between adsorption before and after regeneration is due to the change in

385 the zeolite's cationic composition on the surface. The cationic composition of the SWW before

386 and after adsorption in Method 1 (see **supplementary material**) showed there was a net
387 desorption of Na^+ (linked to the displacement of Na^+ ions naturally present on the zeolite by
388 NH_4^+), and a net adsorption of K^+ , while Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} remained stable. The affinity of these
389 ions to a cation exchange surface generally follows the order of $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{K}^+ > \text{NH}_4^+ > \text{Na}^+$
390 (Pinelli et al. 2022), which explains the net desorption of Na^+ and adsorption of K^+ . Despite their
391 higher potential for selectivity, Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} were not adsorbed from SWW, attributable to the
392 larger size of their hydrated radius, compared to Na^+ and K^+ . Their size decreases their potential
393 to adsorb to microporous materials, like zeolite, due to the steric hindrance limiting their access
394 to the pores (Pinelli et al. 2022). Thus, the competition of these cations with ammonium has been
395 found to follow the order of $\text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Ca}^{2+}$ (Fu et al. 2022). In Method 2, the cations behaved in a
396 similar manner in the first adsorption cycle, while in the adsorption cycle after the regeneration
397 step, there was a net adsorption of Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} by the zeolite and a net desorption of K^+
398 (with its concentration in SWW increasing by 6.5 times). This change in adsorption behaviour, is
399 due to the difficulty for the NH_4^+ to displace K^+ from the zeolite surface (compared to Na^+)
400 when it is changed to K^+ form (Z-K) during KCl regeneration, since the ionic affinity of K^+ to a
401 cation exchange surface is higher than NH_4^+ .

402 In Method 2, the regeneration step was fractionated in two steps in order to collect a first
403 fraction of N concentrate (i.e., BVs 0-1 of the regeneration solution) and a fraction of K
404 concentrate after the full regeneration of the zeolites column (BVs 1.1- 40 BVs). The N content
405 in the first and second fraction of regeneration effluent obtained was much more diluted than in
406 the N-saturated zeolite (from both methods), with N concentration factors of 36.2 and 1.0,
407 respectively. A maximum N concentration factor of 50 was achieved in the regeneration effluent
408 at 0.15 BV. Therefore, even if a volume of <1 BV is harvested as the first fraction, the resulting

409 product would remain half as concentrated as the N-saturated zeolite. Still, the regeneration
410 effluent represented only 28% of the SWW volume. In conclusion, Method 1 performed better
411 than Method 2, as it generated a significantly lower volume of outputs with higher N content for
412 a given amount of SWW treated (Table 2).

413 Regarding required input quantity, Method 2 required an input of 1,05 BV/mg N
414 recovered (1,02 BV of 3% KCl and 0,03 BV of zeolite per mg N recovered); while Method 1
415 consumes only 0,04 BV of input (zeolite) per mg N recovered. This also translates into less
416 volume of outputs generated by Method 1, which can make their management easier. Method 2
417 would also require more storage and process control equipment related to column regeneration.
418 Moreover, the average market price of natural zeolite is between 2017-2021 was US\$125-140
419 per ton (Crangle, 2022) while the cost of KCl (60%, agricultural grade) ranged between US\$
420 200-300 in the same period, peaking to over US\$ 1000 between 2021-2023 (Brownlie et al.,
421 2024). These translate into a current consumer price range between US\$ 854-1696 for zeolite
422 ([ChemLV](#); [Zeolithkaufen](#)) and US\$ 3674-17039 for KCl of 99% purity ([Lerochem](#); [Merck](#)). For a
423 given bed volume, the cost of each adsorption cycle (without zeolite regeneration) is then
424 estimated to cost about 4-25 times less than each adsorption-regeneration cycle. Therefore,
425 avoiding zeolite regeneration could result in lower investment and operational costs, especially
426 considering the very low cost of zeolite. On the contrary, regenerating the zeolite could be
427 preferable when it is not feasible to transfer the N-saturated zeolite to a buyer, given that
428 regeneration effluent could be easily recirculated to the biological treatment system in an
429 MWWTP or otherwise applied on farmland for irrigation/fertigation purposes. Furthermore, the
430 number of adsorption-regeneration cycles that can be applied before WWT capacity and q_b
431 deteriorate must still be defined. In this study, the ammonium RmE and content on the N-

432 saturated zeolite diminished by 11 and 16%, respectively after the first regeneration cycle.
433 However, the decrease could be attributed to the fact that Z-O adsorbs $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ more efficiently
434 than Z-K, due to the described changes in affinity to competing cations. Z-Na has also been
435 previously shown to have an improved N adsorption capacity compared to Z-K (Pinelli et al.,
436 2022). As Z-Na can be regenerated at least seven times before a significant decrease in
437 breakthrough volume and q_b (Sheikh et al., 2023), this might also be achievable with Z-K. In this
438 scenario, regeneration costs could be mitigated by reusing the KCl solution.

439 3.1.3. Municipal wastewater treatment and production of alternative fertilising products

440 The treatment of HRAS/CS effluent from the pilot SBR with adsorption Methods 1 and 2
441 achieved a TN and COD average RmE of $75 \pm 2\%$ and $48 \pm 6\%$, respectively. Method 2 showed a
442 drop of 32% in BV treated after regeneration (Table 2). The RmE achieved after treating MWW
443 with HRAS/CS+A for TN and COD are even higher (73-82% and 74-82%, respectively), given
444 the HRAS/CS system removes a small percentage of TN ($22 \pm 6\%$) as well as over half of the
445 COD content ($58 \pm 7\%$) in the MWW. The adsorption system removed a fraction of the
446 remaining COD due to the zeolite's capacity to filter out particulate (and some soluble) COD.
447 Therefore, the two-stage system produced an effluent that met dischargeable limits for TN
448 (Section 2.2.1) and COD (70% removal, <125 mg/L) according to the UWWTD. The RmEs of
449 these parameters were also quite close to Flemish standards (minimum 75 and 80% for COD and
450 TN, respectively). Operational parameters would need to be adapted to meet the more stringent
451 discharge limits that might be enforced by the revision of the UWWTD (European Commission,
452 2022b), by working at lower flow rates or treating less MWW per adsorption cycle. When using
453 HRAS/CS effluent, RcE was often higher than RmE. This might be due to bacterial activity that
454 promotes the ammonification of organic N present in MWW (Stefanakis et al. 2014), releasing
455 more $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ that can adsorb to the zeolite.

456 Standards for TP were far from being met, with an average TP removal of only $32 \pm 7\%$,
457 given that the HRAS/CS system can only remove up to 38% of TP (Rahman et al., 2020) and
458 zeolites can only bind anionic species if they are modified (Lu et al., 2022). The TSS RmE of
459 the HRAS system ($67 \pm 12\%$) was also below current UWWTD standards (90% RmE and < 35
460 mg/L). TSS reduction before N adsorption is important because it reduces the lifetime of the
461 column, since it can cause clogging. To simultaneously improve TP and TSS removal, coagulants
462 such as FeCl_3 or $\text{Al}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixed with anionic polyacrylamide could be dosed to the
463 HRAS/CS SBR during the contact phase (Section 2.1), to allow enough contact time for the
464 coagulants to precipitate PO_4^{3-} and flocculate TSS (Cagnetta et al., 2019; Xiao et al., 2023).

465 The N content on the N-saturated zeolites differed for Method 1 depending on whether
466 SWW or HRAS/CS effluent were used as influent, while the N content achieved with Method 2
467 was the same under both conditions. This is due to the fact that initial NH_4^+ -N concentration
468 (Table 2) in HRAS/CS effluent used for Method 1 was either lower or higher than that in SWW,
469 while both the initial NH_4^+ -N concentration and competing cation concentrations in the
470 HRAS/CS effluent used for Method 2 was very similar to that in SWW. As the C_o of NH_4^+ -N
471 increased, the q_b also increased (Table 2), a behaviour also reported in literature up to a C_o of
472 2000 mg/L (depending on the type of zeolite) (Jmayai et al., 2018). The N content in the
473 regeneration effluents produced with Method 2 was quite low, similarly to the products obtained
474 with SWW (Table 2). The K^+ content in Method 2 outputs (Table 3) demonstrates that a large
475 fraction of the K^+ in the KCl adsorbed to Z-O, modifying the zeolite to Z-K. This increased the
476 K^+ content in the N-saturated zeolites by 0.6% DW, compared to those produced with Method 1
477 (Table 3). The K^+ content detected on the N-saturated zeolites produced with Method 1 is found

478 naturally in Z-O zeolite. K mineralisation potential tests should be carried out to determine the
 479 total K fraction extractable from the zeolite, and thus its accessibility to plants as a nutrient.

480 **Table 3.** Physicochemical characterization of adsorption outputs (alternative fertilising products)
 481 generated when using effluent from the HRAS/CS pilot system.

Parameters	Alternative fertilising products				
	N-saturated zeolite (C _o = 12.0)	N-saturated zeolite (C _o = 36.1)	N-saturated zeolite ^a (C _o = 24.9)	Regeneration effluent (C _o = 27.9)	
				Fraction 1	Fraction 2
TOC (% DW)	0.08 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.00	NA	NA
COD (mg/L)	NA	NA	NA	ND	54.67 ± 2.52
Humidity (%)	23.49 ± 1.41	22.36 ± 0.89	27.62 ± 0.75	NA	NA
pH (-)	7.22 ± 0.03	6.82 ± 0.13	6.98 ± 0.05	6.26 ± 0.20	6.23 ± 0.06
EC (µS/cm)	ND	85.8 ± 11.1	54.2 ± 13.7	ND	4.5E+04 ± 2.2E+04
Macronutrients (% FW)					
NH ₄ ⁺ -N	0.139 ± 0.010	0.235 ± 0.003	0.155 ± 0.001	0.078 ± 0.002	0.006 ± 0.000
NO ₃ ⁻ /NO ₂ ⁻	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	ND	<0.001
TN	0.145 ± 0.015	0.260 ± 0.008	0.165 ± 0.001	ND	0.006 ± 0.001
TP	0.015 ± 0.001	0.014 ± 0.000	0.014 ± 0.001	0.072 ± 0.050	0.016 ± 0.007
TS	<0.017	0.014 ± 0.000	0.012 ± 0.000	0.999 ± 0.010	0.083 ± 0.003
Ca	1.32 ± 0.04	0.92 ± 0.01	0.77 ± 0.00	0.07 ± 0.01	4.04E-3 ± 0.12E-3
Mg	0.30 ± 0.02	0.31 ± 0.00	0.31 ± 0.00	4.27E-3 ± 0.54E-3	2.10E-4 ± 0.07E-4
Na	0.27 ± 0.00	0.23 ± 0.01	0.16 ± 0.00	0.11 ± 0.02	3.53E-3 ± 0.23E-3
K	1.40 ± 0.05	1.48 ± 0.01	1.83 ± 0.01	0.16 ± 0.02	1.43 ± 0.00
Micronutrients (mg/kg DW or mg/L^b)					
B	<49.66	<16.20	<16.46	2.42 ± 0.69	0.90 ± 0.53
Co	6.61 ± 0.67	0.72 ± 0.14	0.77 ± 0.10	<0.015	<0.010
Cu	1.21 ± 0.08	2.08 ± 0.30	4.29 ± 2.21	<0.024	<0.017
Fe	8151.08 ± 126.11	7918.31 ± 158.44	8111.74 ± 116.00	0.07 ± 0.04	<0.014
Mn	184.04 ± 67.53	194.08 ± 60.71	180.26 ± 47.91	2.33 ± 0.32	0.09 ± 0.00
Zn	32.60 ± 8.56	27.51 ± 0.77	36.15 ± 8.74	0.05 ± 0.04	<0.013
Contaminants (mg/kg DW)					
As	< 49.66	<16.20	<16.46	<0.29	<0.20
Cd	<2.09	<0.90	<0.91	<0.02	<0.01
Cr	10.98 ± 0.12	7.879 ± 0.37	7.979 ± 0.05	<0.013	<0.09
Ni	12.03 ± 0.78	2.78 ± 0.46	2.68 ± 1.13	<0.032	0.02 ± 0.01
Pb	17.60 ± 2.53	19.33 ± 6.36	18.58 ± 2.03	<0.07	<0.05

482 C_o = initial NH₄⁺-N concentration (mg/L); DW = dry weight; FW = fresh weight; NA = Not applicable; ND = Not
 483 determined (due to insufficient sample availability)

484 ^a After a regeneration cycle

485 ^b N-saturated zeolite in mg/kg DW, regeneration effluent in mg/L

486 The q_b of Z-O and Z-K achieved in this study is generally lower than those achieved in
487 other similar trials for N removal from MWW (3.2-33 mg/g DW) (Castro et al., 2021; Guaya et
488 al., 2016; Maghfiroh et al., 2023; Pinelli et al., 2022; Sheikh et al., 2023). This is due to the fact
489 that MWW with higher C_o of NH_4^+ -N was applied (between 34-5000 mg/L). These findings
490 highlight that the zeolite column's adsorption capacity is far from being exhausted with the N
491 recovery methods tested, which is mainly due to the low C_o of NH_4^+ -N in the HRAS/CS effluent
492 used. This leaves room for increasing N content on the zeolite without recurring to its
493 modification, namely by using higher strength MWWT side-streams such as LFD (Figure 1), in
494 line with this research's aim to generate fertilising products with low reagent inputs.

495 From these results, HRAS/CS+A proved to be a technically feasible process for WWT
496 and N recovery, by successfully up-concentrating the N present in MWW and producing effluent
497 that met current TN and COD discharge limits. However, to determine the overall feasibility of
498 the HRAS/CS+A process, economic and life cycle assessments of this process must still be
499 performed to determine the economic feasibility and energy and carbon footprint of the process.
500 The HRAS/CS and adsorption technologies were chosen for this study because they have
501 potential to be more economically feasible and sustainable, when compared to the CAS
502 technology that is generally applied in WWTPs, based on the fact that (i) the HRAS process can
503 be implemented in the existing infrastructure of WWTPs (Rahman et al., 2020), (ii) the
504 HRAS/CS process can recover more energy from MWW as biogas than the CAS process
505 (Meerburg et al., 2015) and (iii) replacing N removal from MWW by nitrification-denitrification
506 with N recovery via adsorption reduces the energy demand and N_2O emissions of a WWTP, due
507 to the decrease in the need for aeration (Ahn et al., 2010; Zessner et al., 2010) and low cost and
508 energy use of the adsorption process (Huang et al., 2018).

509 **3.2 Enhancing nitrogen recovery with high-strength wastewater: liquid fraction of sewage**
510 **sludge digestate**

511 In order to enhance N recovery from the WWT process, Method 1b (Section 2.3) adds
512 LFD (a higher strength wastewater than HRAS/CS effluent) as influent to the adsorption column.
513 Method 1b was tested because the results from Section 3.1 showed that the adsorption outputs
514 had low N content due to the low NH_4^+ -N concentration of the HRAS/CS effluent (12-36 mg/L).
515 Method 1b produced N-saturated zeolites that had an N content 4.4 times higher than the those
516 produced with Methods 1 and 2 (Table 2). This was achieved after treating 140 BV of synthetic
517 HRAS/CS effluent, followed by only 30 BV of LFD (Section 2.1). A 25% NH_4^+ -N RmE and
518 RcE from LFD were achieved (according to C_c), without signs of N loss from stripping, despite
519 the higher pH of the synthetic LFD.

520 The experimental q_{\max} (8.3 ± 0.1 mg/g FW, 80 BV treated) was the same as the N content
521 on the N-saturated zeolites obtained from Method 1b, showing that the latter were fully saturated
522 after treating 30 BV of synthetic LFD. When treating only 5 BV of LFD, the N RmE reached
523 76% (according to C_c), while the N adsorbed on the zeolites (derived from the mass balance) was
524 3.6 mg/g FW. Therefore, between 5-30 BV of LFD can be treated to increase zeolite N content,
525 while achieving a certain degree of N removal from LFD. These results show that with Method
526 1b it was possible to treat and recover N from both HRAS/CS effluent and LFD with the same
527 adsorption column. To further enhance the RcE and Rme of NH_4^+ -N from LFD, batch
528 incubations downstream from HRAS/CS effluent treatment could also be tested since higher
529 adsorption capacities can be reached under batch conditions (He et al., 2022). Removing N from
530 LFD generated in CAS systems is beneficial because it is generally recirculated to the headworks

531 of a WWTP, increasing the N load on the system. Applying zeolite adsorption would then reduce
532 the need for oxygen supply, subsequently reducing N₂O emissions, at a low cost.

533 **3.3 Market potential of wastewater treatment-derived fertilising products in Europe**

534 The outputs obtained from the HRAS/CS+A process were evaluated as potential
535 fertilising products in terms of the guidelines set by the FPR. In order to be marketable under the
536 FPR, a product must comply with requirements related to their product function category (PFC)
537 and component material category (CMC). Regarding PFCs, none of the products could function
538 as an organic fertilizer, given that their organic C content (as expressed by TOC or COD) is less
539 than 7.5% (for solids) and 3% (for liquids) for N-saturated zeolites and regeneration effluent,
540 respectively (Table 3). Despite the strategies used to enhance N and K content on the N-saturated
541 zeolites (Method 1b and regeneration with KCl), the products' primary macronutrient content (N
542 and K) is far below the minimum requirements to fit the PFC for straight (10 or 12% by mass of
543 TN or K₂O, respectively) or compound (3% by mass of TN and K₂O) solid inorganic fertilisers.
544 It has been observed that the q_{\max} of Slovakian zeolite stabilises below an N content of 3% when
545 applying a solution with NH₄⁺-N C₀ above 1300 mg/L (Jmayai et al., 2018), meaning that even if
546 the q_{\max} is attained, it will not meet the TN requirements for a solid inorganic macronutrient
547 fertiliser. The regeneration effluent also did not meet the standards for straight (5 or 3% by mass
548 of TN or K₂O, respectively) or compound (1.5% by mass of TN and K₂O) liquid inorganic
549 fertilizer. The micronutrient content in Method 1 and 2 products (from Section 3.1.3) was also
550 characterized (Table 3), showing that their sum does not add up to the minimum requirement
551 (5% by dry weight) for the PFC of compound inorganic micronutrient fertiliser.

552 Nevertheless, the N-saturated zeolite produced from HRAS/CS effluent treatment has the
553 potential to fit various PFCs. Given that fresh zeolite is considered a classical soil improver
554 (Alessandrino et al., 2022), shown to improve the soil's water holding capacity under certain

555 conditions (Ibrahim and Alghamdi, 2021), the N-saturated zeolite could be tested for its
556 efficiency as inorganic soil improver (PFC 3[B]). It could also be tested for its efficiency as
557 growing medium (PFC 4), because fresh zeolite has been previously applied in substrate
558 mixtures for plants (Bondi et al., 2023). Fresh zeolite has also been found to reduce the
559 conversion of NH_4^+ into NO_3^- (Torma et al., 2014), thus N-saturated zeolite could also function
560 as nitrification inhibitor [PFC 5(A)]. The proposed mechanism for the inhibition is that the
561 zeolite's microporous structure prevents nitrifying microorganisms from accessing the adsorbed
562 NH_4^+ -N in the pores, while this NH_4^+ -N remains accessible for root uptake (Torma et al., 2014).
563 In this way, the zeolite aids in the prevention of N leaching and could provide slow-release N &
564 K. Finally, the use of N-saturated zeolite as (non)microbial plant stimulant (PFC 6[A] and [B])
565 under crop stress conditions could also be investigated (Bybordi, 2016). Future studies could
566 identify whether microbes that could stimulate plant growth are carried over from MWW onto
567 the zeolite (to fit under PFC 6 [A]).

568 For PFCs 3(B), 4 and 6(A and B), limit values are established in the FPR for certain
569 contaminants, micronutrients and pathogens. Regarding the limit values of contaminants, the N-
570 saturated zeolite complies with limits for Cu, Zn, Cd, Ni, Pb and As for PFC 3(B) and PFC 4
571 categories (Table 3). However, further characterization is necessary to confirm the absence of the
572 regulated pathogens for these PFCs (including PFC 6) and to determine the amount of Hg and Cr
573 (VI) in the products (given their total Cr value is above the limits for Cr[VI]). If Hg, Cr (VI) and
574 pathogen results comply with the FPR, the products can be tested in the soil to determine their
575 effect as soil improver, plant stimulant or growing medium. Fertilising product blends (PFC 7)
576 could also be an option. For example, blending solid N-saturated zeolite with ammonium

577 sulphate from NH₃ stripping and scrubbing of LFD could enhance the product's marketability by
578 blending two different PFCs in the same product (e.g., nitrification inhibitor and fertiliser).

579 In the case of the regeneration effluent, characterization results show that it should be
580 considered for irrigation or as a component in fertigation water, rather than a fertilising product.
581 In this case, there would be no need for a fractionated regeneration step, and the 40 BVs of
582 regeneration effluent could be collected together, containing about 60 ppm of N and 1.4 % K.
583 The WRR opens the opportunity for using reclaimed water containing nutrients for irrigation, to
584 restore nutrients to natural biogeochemical cycles. Therefore, treated wastewater effluent to be
585 used for irrigation could be mixed with regeneration effluent to provide both water and nutrients
586 to plants. In order to determine if the HRAS/CS+A system's treated and regeneration effluents
587 would enter into one of the reclaimed water quality classes (A-D, as defined by WRR), the
588 system must be up-scaled to obtain a large-enough volume of outputs that can be characterized
589 for pathogens, BOD₅, TSS and turbidity. Moreover, a mechanism for reducing TP content in a
590 HRAS/CS+A system would also have to be chosen and tested, such as coagulant dosing in the
591 SBR contact phase. If the regeneration effluent and treated wastewater fit into a reclaimed water
592 quality class, on-farm units of HRAS/CS+A could also be foreseen in order to treat the domestic
593 wastewater in farms, which could then be reused domestically and for irrigation.

594 Finally, in order for a product to be marketable under the FPR, it must also fit into a
595 CMC. At the moment, neither the N-saturated zeolite nor the regeneration effluent would fit into
596 an existing CMC. However, it is possible to amend the FPR in the coming years in order to
597 include more CMCs, as was the case for CMCs 12-15. Therefore, it is important to evaluate the
598 performance of HRAS/CS+A outputs as potential fertilising products. If positive results are

599 obtained, a new CMC could be proposed, encompassing these products, as well as other nutrient-
600 rich products derived from an adsorption process treating waste streams.

601 Taking into account that the direct adsorption outputs from N recovery with the
602 HRAS/CS+A process do not fit into PFC 1 (fertilisers), efforts in N recovery with this system
603 should focus on maximizing WWT efficiency and minimizing costs, since (i) there are various
604 other PFCs the resulting products can be marketed under and (ii) the environmental and
605 economic gains at the level of the WWTP will outweigh the impact of the N recovery on the
606 products. Future research on outputs from similar N recovery systems should also focus on
607 testing the efficiency of zeolite (or other natural packing materials) as a fertilising product
608 corresponding to PFCs 3-6, rather than further maximizing the N content in the adsorption
609 outputs to meet PFC 1 requirements.

610 **4. Conclusions**

611 Despite the high up-concentration of NH_4^+ -N achieved by zeolites adsorption and the
612 high adsorption of K^+ from KCl regeneration, the final N and K content of the fertilising
613 products was too low for PFC 1 (for all flow rates and N recovery methods applied). Still, the N-
614 saturated zeolites have potential to be marketed as PFC 3-6 products, while regeneration effluent
615 could be applied in fertigation. Therefore, efforts to optimise the HRAS/CS+A system in a larger
616 scale should focus on comparing the tested methods in terms of cost, inputs and energy
617 reduction, rather than the final N content in the products.

618 “E-supplementary data of this work can be found in online version of the paper”.

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623 **6. Data Availability**

624 Data will be made available on request.

625 **7. References**

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757 **Appendix**758 **Table A.1**

759 Cation content in synthetic wastewater (SWW) and HRAS C/S effluent before and after
 760 applying an N recovery method. ND=Not determined

Method	Cation concentrations (mg/L)									
	NH ₄ ⁺ -N		K ⁺		ND ⁺		Ca ⁺		Mg	
	Influent	Effluent	Influent	Effluent	Influent	Effluent	Influent	Effluent	Influent	Effluent
<i>Synthetic Wastewater</i>										
Method 1	23.7 ± 0.5	5.0 ± 0.2	21.8	17.4 ± 0.2	104.5	134.1 ± 0.9	78.2	80.4 ± 0.4	8.0	7.9 ± 0.1
Method 2 (First saturation cycle)	23.3 ± 1.4 ^c	4.6 ± 1.1	23.4	15.2 ± 0.3	106.4	135.0 ± 1.7	79.1	80.4 ± 1.3	8.1	8.2 ± 0.0
Method 2 (Second saturation cycle)	23.3 ± 1.4 ^c	6.6 ± 0.6	23.4	154.3 ± 10.9	106.4	86.5 ± 0.1	79.1	60.3 ± 2.2	8.1	7.6 ± 0.0
<i>HRAS/CS effluent</i>										
Method 1	12.01 ± 1.36	2.6 ± 0.1	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Method 1	36.15 ± 4.03	5.0 ± 0.2	11.7 ± 1.5	22.5 ± 1.5	52.8 ± 6.9	156.7 ± 2.5	38.1 ± 3.1	92.5 ± 2.3	4.3 ± 0.5	9.2 ± 0.1
Method 2 (First saturation cycle)	27.93 ± 0.12	5.0 ± 0.3	12.1 ± 2.7	16.6 ± 1.9	61.2 ± 14.1	121.1 ± 14.2	73.8 ± 17.0	88.5 ± 4.2	6.0 ± 1.4	8.3 ± 0.9
Method 2 (Second saturation cycle)	24.95 ± 1.77	4.5 ± 0.6	19.5 ± 0.2	175.7 ± 31	97.5 ± 2.1	70.4 ± 4.4	84.8 ± 3.2	66.1 ± 5.9	9.1 ± 0.1	7.3 ± 0.4

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